

DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF HELICAL GEAR PAIRS BY EXPERIMENTAL AND FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Gear is one of the most common & important machine components in many advanced machines due to their unique technical advantages. Gears are widely used in various applications such as automobiles, aircrafts, heavy machinery & marine vehicles. Gears have many functions including reducing speed, increasing available torque or changing the direction of power transmission. Spur and helical gears are called parallel-axis gear as they are mounted on parallel axis. Helical gear pairs generate lower magnitude of dynamic load due to gradual pick-up of load during the gear tooth action.

In spite of the many function of gears, noise and vibration continue to cause major troubles within their applications with the increasing demands of high speed, heavy transmission, lightweight & quiet running in modern geared systems, the reduction of noise and vibration becomes more and more important.

Several researchers have been performed the studies on dynamic behavior of gear systems for two primary reasons, **one reason** is that vibration levels of the gear system are directly related to the noise levels associated with it. Dynamic gear mesh forces created at gear mesh interfaces are transmitted to surrounding structures through bearing and gear box housing to form primary source of gear noise. The **second reason** for studying gear dynamics has been durability and strength of the gear pair. Forces acting at the gear meshes and bearings under high-speed conditions are typically than those under low-operating conditions. As a result of this, tooth bending stresses and contact stresses are influenced by its dynamic behavior.

Normally, gear systems are designed using static analysis. However, when gears systems operate at high speeds, there are several factors which affect gear performance. There is no agreement among researchers on the best methods for evaluating dynamic load effects. Hence, gear designers are confronted with conflicting theories. They generally have relay upon the past experiences, services, safety factors and experimental data with limited range of applicability.

Gear systems composed of several parts such as gear-pairs bearings, shafts and casings. Several factors of gears, Shifts, bearing and casings have non-negligible amount of influence on its dynamic performance. Therefore, dynamic analysis of gear pair becoming one of the important step in gear design. Several critical performance parameters of gears, such as noise, vibration reliable and fatigue are closely related with dynamics. In this proposed research vibration levels will be measured to investigate the effect of quality of gears on its dynamic performance. An improved understanding of vibration signal is required for the early detection of incipient gear failure to achieve high reliability. The ability to accurately calculate the dynamic loads in geared systems becomes essential for advanced transmission design.

Normally Thirteen types of precision grades of gears are standardized, which are arranged from low to high by numbers 0 to 12. These standard are defined by DIN which refers various parameters for gear, gear tooth and gear flank. A lower quality class indicates higher geometrical accuracy and vice versa.

These grades refer to quality of gears in terms of permissible limits of deviations. Gear quality grades are standardized for different module ranges and different pitch circle

diameters in AGMA, DIN, JIS and other standards. As per literature review it is clearly observed that tooth surface is one of important parameter that affects on gear vibration and noise.

In order to demonstrate the effect of accuracy of gear tooth surface or quality grades of helical gear pair, it is decided that various tests or experiments will be conducted by using specially designed and constructed Dynamic Test Setup. Accelerometer will be mounted on location and direction identified through Sweep Test. After identifying location of accelerometer on gear box it is necessary to predict natural frequency of gear box in assembled condition. Natural frequency will be predicted experimentally by using Impact Hammer Test and vibration signals acquired by mounting accelerometer.

During test, vibrations signal will be sent to voltage amplifier to match amplify signals before analysis. The frequency spectra will be analyzed by processing time signal through FFT analyzer.

The dynamic response of helical gear pairs will be predicted by using a finite element method. In recent years finite element approach become more popular to study dynamics of gear boxes which have ability to capture non linear dynamics of gear pairs. Finite element analysis is mainly divided into three stages as preprocessing, solution and post processing. Preprocessing includes 3D model and related defined input data, meshing will be done by considering type of element, size and boundary conditions will be applied. Solution stages will solve all equations by using suitable algorithms. Post processing includes results which will be displayed in terms of frequency response curve.

In this dissertation work it is decided to carryout Dynamic Analysis of helical gears of different grades using Vibration analysis and Finite Element Technique.

Ideal involute pair of gear will transmit motion with constant angular velocity ratio. However tooth profile of gear always design with some amount of deviations. In some cases, it is provided due to lubrication and easy motion between pairs of gears. However in many practical applications it is impossible to produce gears without manufacturing errors. Assembly errors also occur during assembly of gears box components should be carried out precisely.

Tooth profile deviation is one of the primary sources of gear noise and vibration. These deviation are also known as tolerances or permissible errors. For economic reasons the values of these tolerances should be selected as high and wide as possible, since unnecessarily precise tolerances makes the gears costlier. Therefore it is imperative for gear designer to acquire the necessary knowledge regarding effect of quality grade and tolerances on its dynamic performance.

As per Indian Standard specification gears have been classified into 10 accuracy grades, from 3 (highly precision gears) to 12 (course quality, low speed gears) Accuracy grades 1 and 2 exist in German Practice, these grades are mainly for master gears and are produced extremely by sophisticated machines. The grade number refers to degree of precision with which the gear teeth have been made. The quality of a gear depends on limits of tolerance for pitch , tooth profile and tooth alignment.

For common engineering applications the grades usually lies between 5 to 10. Many factors have influence on the choice of quality grade such as available testing procedures for accuracy, assembly requirements, and backlash accuracy requirements, precision noise level. Another very important consideration is additional dynamic forces caused by manufacturing errors. Higher quality grade pair expected to run smoothly, lesser error and lower amplitude of vibration level.

Table 1. Some of applications of quality grade gears are as follows:

Sr. No.	Quality Grade	Applications
01	1-2	Master Gears
02	2-4	Measuring Instruments
03	5,6,7	Turbines
04	5-8	Marine Engines, Printing Industries, General M/c
05	7-12	Locomotives, Agriculture Equipments

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

From Literature Review it is concluded that several researchers made attempt to investigate the relationship between the gear parameters and their dynamic behavior. Presently some methods are presented by researchers to minimize the effects of Dynamic Loading. The work on gear quality and its effects are not yet carried out. Also grades of gears affect the dynamic performance behavior of gears. Dynamic analysis in order to study the effect of gear grades on its dynamic behavior is one of important requirement in the study of gears.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To manufacture helical gears of different grades.
2. To design and develop loading fitment for experimental dynamic analysis.
3. To compare results obtained by various methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

A pair of meshing gears with rigid, perfect, uniformly spaced involute Teeth would transmit exactly uniform angular motion. However, the tooth faces of real gears are designed to deviate slightly from perfect involute Surfaces; in addition the teeth elastically deform result in non-involute Action of missing rotating gears.

Over the last several years, a large number of contributions on the behavior of spur and helical gears have been presented by the researchers. They identified the factors that affects on dynamic loading. The nucleus of all these studies is to investigate gear tooth action during missing period. A brief review of some of these studies is presented below.

G. Bonari and F. Pellican [1] presented a method for analysis of non-linear Vibrations of spur gear in presence of manufacturing errors. They develop classical-single-degree-of-freedom model with backlash and time-varying stiffness. Finally, they carried out a dynamic analysis in the case of perfect and imperfect gears, in order to show the effect of profile errors and their variance on gear vibration. They concluded that, even though the variance of profile errors in small, the affect on the dynamics is not negligible.

L. Han et. al. [2] Investigated dynamic responses of helical gear pairs by considering the interaction between friction and time-varying mesh stiffness. For that purpose, they developed 8 degree-of-freedom model including friction excitations. They introduced calculation of friction excitation and influences of working conditions such as surface roughness, transmitted load and speed. The result indicates that, due to interaction vibration displacement along off-line-of-action is not consistent in a whole meshing period.

Y. Li et.al. [3] established dynamic model of a mortar two-stage helical gear transmission system in electric vehicle at constant speed. In this study, the Helix angle is 30.5 degrees. They developed friction model and bench test is carried out to verify the model. From their analysis, they observed that the friction needs to be considered for the analysis of gear systems. The study is good for the reduction of vibration and noise. Also, many provide a theoretical base for the condition monitoring of the gear system in electric vehicles.

Raut A. S., et. al. [4] investigated experimentally the combined influence of geometrical parameters such as tooth addendum, Gear backlash and linear tip-relief Profile modification on the dynamic behavior of spur gear pair. For this purpose, Design and constructed a novel test set-up for measurement of vibration purpose of spur gear pairs. They used statistical technique to investigate the relationship between the geometrical parameters and Vibratory response.

The purpose procedure determines the optimum level of geometrical parameters that minimizes vibration level and, at the same time, is least sensitive to manufacturing variances. Finally, they performed stimulation experiment to validate the conclusion drawn during analysis phase.

J-F. Shi et.al. [5] presented dynamic model of a spur gear pair under multi-state machine conditions such as teeth separation, Drive and back-side tooth mesh. In their model, they included time-wearing mesh stiffness, time-varying friction, load distribution, comprehensive transmission error and backlash. The numerically analyzed variations of the dynamic meshing force under different meshing state. Their results indicate that the complicated phenomena such as drive-side impact, teeth-separation and back-side impact

gradually occur with the decrease of load or the increase of the comprehensive error. However, these phenomena always exist with the increase in backlash.

Prashant Jaysing Patil et. al. [6] investigated effect of helix angle and pressure angle on bending stress in helical gears under dynamic state. The photo stress method has been used as experimental methods. Theoretical analysis was carried out by velocity factor method and Spott's equation. The results show that experimental method gives a bending stress value that is closer to the true value, and bending stress varies with pressure angle and helix angle. The photo stress technique gives clear knowledge of stress pattern at root of tooth.

HELICAL GEAR TERMINOLOGY AND RELATIONS

Because spur gears are easier to design and manufacture, engineers usually prefer these gears when power is transmitted between parallel shafts. However there are some design considerations like greater contact ratio, greater strength, and some operational requirements such as noiselessness, smoother engagement of meshing teeth, for which the use of helical gears is preferred. When a pair of parallel gears mesh, the following conditions must be satisfied for proper running of the set:

- (i) The gears must have helix angles of equal value;
- (ii) The gear teeth of each member must have the same module, and
- (iii) The gear teeth of each member must have opposite helices, that is, one gear must have right-handed helical teeth while the other must have left-handed ones.

One of the fundamental difference between spur and helical gear as far as the course of action is concerned is that the contact of the two spur gears in mesh takes place always in a line extending all along the surface of the tooth, this line being always parallel to the axis of the gear. In a helical gear, the initial contact is a diagonal across the face and flank of the tooth.

The basic parameters of helical gears have been shown in Fig. 1 represents the developed pitch cylinder of a helical gear. The definitions of basic nomenclature and gear tooth terminology are the same in spur and helical gears. The following special parameters of a helical gear are defined here.

Fig 1 Helical Gear Parameters

Fig. 2 Gear Tooth Parameters

Fig. 3 Helical Gear Views and Sections

Fig. 4 a. Reference Profile in Normal and Transverse Sections

Fig. 4 b. Relation between Normal and Transverse Sections
 Fig. 4 c. Front View of Helical Gear

Helix angle (β) : This is the angle which the tooth trace of a helical gear in the pitch plane makes with the gear axis.

Lead angle (γ) : Lead angle is the complimentary angle to the helix angle, is given by, $\gamma = 90^\circ - \beta$

In case of a helical gear, two types of sections are considered – the normal section and transverse section. These sections have been shown in **fig. 4(a)** with respect to the reference profile. The normal section is taken by passing a plane at right angles to the tooth traces of the top-most tooth and through the pitch point on the cylinder as shown in **fig. 4 (a)**. If the plane is passed at right angles to the axis of the gear, transverse section is obtained. Normal section of the pitch cylinder is an ellipse while the transverse section is a circle.

Module: Two kinds of modules are differentiated in helical gears – the normal module and transverse module. They bear the following relation to each other

$$m_t = \frac{m_n}{\cos \beta} \quad \text{where, } m_t = \text{the transverse module, } m_n \text{ or } m = \text{normal module.}$$

Circular pitch: Normal Circular pitch, P_n or $P = \pi m$

Transverse Circular pitch, $P_t = \pi m_t$

$$\text{Axial pitch: } P_a = \pi m_a = \pi m_t \tan \gamma = \pi m_t \cot \beta = \frac{\pi m}{\cos \gamma} = \frac{H}{z}$$

Where $H = \text{Lead}$, and $z = \text{Number of teeth}$

Base pitch: Normal base pitch, $P_{bn} = P_n \cos \alpha$

Transverse base pitch, $P_{bt} = P_t \cos \alpha$

Pressure angle: In case of helical gear, it is important to differentiate between the normal pressure angle α or (α_n) , which is the pressure angle in a plane perpendicular to the tooth trace (normal section), the transverse pressure angle α_t , which is the pressure angle in a plane perpendicular to the gear axis (transverse section). The pressure angles are related as,

$\tan \alpha = \tan \alpha_t \cos \beta$, The normal pressure angle α is 20° for standard tooth profile.

Face advance: It can be defined as the distance on the pitch circle through which helical tooth moves from the initial position at which the contact begins at one end of the tooth curve to the final position at the other end across the face width when the contact ceases. The face advance of a helical gear is created due to the helical orientation of the course of the tooth along its length and this off-set is given by, $FA = b \times \tan \beta$

The above relation can be established from fig1, where $b =$ width of the gear. Obviously, the face advance of a spur gear is zero. In a parallel helical gear, width b is made larger with a view to making the face advance greater than the circular pitch corresponding to a given helix angle. This ensures continuous contact in the axial plane as the gears rotate. The ratio – face advance to circular pitch (in transverse section) – can be considered as a contact ratio (termed “face contact ratio”), and along with the regular contact ratio as in the case of spur gears. For the sake of safety, it is customary to increase the limiting value of tooth-width by at least 15 % (the limiting condition being $FA = P$), so that $b > \frac{1.15 P}{\tan \beta}$

Lead: It is the axial advance of the helix in one complete turn.

Pitch circle diameter: In a helical gear, because of helix angle, the pitch circle diameter and other diameters are greater than those of the corresponding spur gear. It has been pointed out before that the transverse section only is circular, the normal one being elliptical. In **Fig 4 (c)** a front view of a helical gear is shown. This is the same as a transverse section. It is to be emphasized here that irrespective of the section, the pitch cylinder remain the same, whose diameter is given by

$$d = \frac{Z m}{\cos \beta} = z m_t = z m \sec \beta$$

Tip circle diameter: In spur gear, the tip circle is given by, $d_a = z m + 2m$

In helical gear, the tip circle is given by, $d_a = z m_t + 2m$

The tip circle diameter of helical gear is not given as, $d_a = z m_t + 2m$

The reason is quite apparent from Fig. 4 (c). It is a circle only in the transverse section and, therefore, to reach the tip circle one has to add an amount equal to m on both sides of d radially from the center, so that

$$\bar{S} \text{ (or } \bar{S}_n) = \bar{S}_t \cos \beta$$

The basic relations of a helical gear pair in mesh are given in table. The gears are normal ones conforming to the basic rack.

Contact Ratio of Helical Gears: Due to the effect of the face advance in a helical in a helical gear, an extra amount of contact ratio is created. This face advance is due to the helical orientation of the tooth along the length of the tooth, covering the width of the gear. The ratio due to the face advance is called the face contact ratio (also known as the axial contact ratio and overlap contact ratio) and is given by

$$CR_{FA} = \frac{\text{Face advance}}{\text{Transverse circular pitch}} = \frac{b \tan \beta}{P_t}, \quad P_t = \frac{\pi m}{\cos \beta}$$

$$\therefore CR_{FA} = \frac{b \tan \beta}{\pi m} \cos \beta = \frac{b \sin \beta}{\pi m}$$

Due to the face contact ratio, the total contact ratio in case of a helical gear is greater than that of a spur gear. The transverse contact ratio in case of a helical gear in mesh can be found in a similar manner as in case of spur gears. It is given by

$$CR_T = \frac{\sqrt{r_{a1}^2 - r_{b1}^2} + \sqrt{r_{a2}^2 - r_{b2}^2} - a \sin \alpha_t}{P_{bt}}$$

The total contact ratio of the helical gearing is a summation of above two contact ratios. Therefore

$$CR = CR_{FA} + CR_T$$

$$CR = \frac{b \tan \beta}{P_t} + \frac{\sqrt{r_{a1}^2 - r_{b1}^2} + \sqrt{r_{a2}^2 - r_{b2}^2} - a \sin \alpha_t}{P_{bt}}$$

Transverse base pitch, $P_{bt} = \text{Transverse circular pitch, } P_t \times \cos \alpha_t$

The above equation of contact ratio can be written as

$$CR = \frac{b \sin \beta \cos \alpha_t + \cos \beta [\sqrt{r_{a1}^2 - r_{b1}^2} + \sqrt{r_{a2}^2 - r_{b2}^2} - a \sin \alpha_t]}{\pi m \cos \alpha_t}$$

DESIGN OF HELICAL GEAR

Helical Gear Pair is designed according to the Power transmission requirement for that purpose standard reference books are referred and module and centre distance is fixed.

Table 2. Standard Design Parameters of the Helical Gear Pairs

Sr. No	Description	Formula	Values
1	Norma module, mm	m_n	2.00
3	Gear ratio	i	1 : 1
3	Helix angle, deg	β	20
4	Lead angle, deg	$\gamma = 90^\circ - \beta$	66.44
5	Face width, mm	b	30
11	Pitch circle diameter, (d) mm	$d_1 = \frac{z_1 m}{\cos \beta} = z_1 m_t$	84.11
12	Tip circle diameter, (d_{a1}), mm	$d_{a1} = d_1 + 2m$	88.11
13	Base circle diameter (d_{b1}), mm	$d_{b1} = d_1 \cos \alpha_t$	80
14	Root circle diameter (d_{t1}), mm	$d_{t1} = d_1 - 2 \times 1.25 m$	79.11
15	Center distance, mm	$a_o = \frac{(d_1 + d_2)}{2}$ $= \left(\frac{m}{\cos \beta} \right) \times \frac{z_1 + z_2}{2}$	84.11
16	No. of teeth	Z	40
18	Material	-	EN 8

SHAFT DESIGN

Introduction : Transmission shafts are used in virtually every piece of rotating machinery to transmit rotary motion and torque from one location to another. Sometimes shafts will carry gears, sheaves (pulleys) or sprockets, which transmit the rotary motion via mating gears, belts or chains from shaft to shaft. Shafts are carried in bearings, in a simply supported (straddle-mounted) configuration, cantilevered or overhung, depending on the machine configuration.

Shaft Loads: The loading on rotating shafts is principally one of two ways: torsion due to the transmitted torque or bending from transverse loads at gears, sheaves and sprockets. These loads often occur in combination, for example, the transmitted torque may be associated may be associated with forces at the teeth of gears or sprockets attached to the shafts. The character of both the torque and bending loads may be either steady (constant)

or may vary with time. Steady and time-varying torque and bending loads can also occur in any combination on the same shaft.

A rotating shaft subjected to a steady, transverse-bending load will experience a fully reverse stress state. Any one stress element on the shaft surface goes from tension to compression each cycle as the shaft turns. Thus, even for steady bending loads, a rotating shaft must be designed against fatigue failure. If either or both the torque and transverse loads vary with time, the fatigue loading becomes more complex.

The most general shaft loading case is that of a fluctuating torque and a fluctuating moment in combination. There can be axial loads if the shaft is fitted with helical or worm gears. Both torque and moment can be time varying and can have both mean and alternating components. The combination of a bending moment and a torque on a rotating shaft creates multi-axial stresses. Any locations along the length of the shaft that appear to have large moments and/or torques (especially if in combination with stress concentrations) need to be examined for possible stress failure and the cross-sectional dimensions or material properties adjusted accordingly.

Attachments and Stress Concentrations: It is most common for shafts to have a number of steps or shoulders, where the diameter changes to accommodate attached elements such as bearings, sprockets, gears etc. Steps or shoulders are necessary to provide accurate and consistent axial location of the attached elements as well as to create the proper diameter to fit standard parts such as bearings. Keys, snap rings, or cross-pins are often used to secure attached elements to the shaft in order to transmit the required torque or to capture the part axially. Keys require a groove in both shaft and part and may need a setscrew to prevent axial motion. Snap rings groove the shaft, and cross-pins create a hole through the shaft. Each of these changes in contour will contribute some stress concentration and must be accounted for the fatigue-stress calculations for the shaft.

Shaft Materials: In order to minimize deflections, steel is the logical choice for a shaft material because of its high modulus of elasticity, though cast or nodular iron is sometimes also used, especially if gears or other attachments are integrally cast with the shaft. Bronze or stainless steel is sometimes used for marine or other corrosive environments. Most machine shafts are made from low-to medium-carbon steel, either cold rolled or hot rolled, though alloy steels are also used where their higher strengths are needed. Cold-rolled steel

is more often used for smaller diameter shafts and hot-rolled used for larger sizes. The same alloy when cold rolled has higher mechanical properties than if hot rolled due to the cold working, but this comes at the cost of residual tensile stresses in the surface. Machining for keyways, grooves, or steps relieves these residual stresses locally and can cause warping. Hot-rolled bars must be machined all over to remove the carburized outer layer, whereas portions of a cold-rolled surface can be left as-rolled except where machining to size is needed for bearings.

Shaft Power: In any rotating system, instantaneous power is the product of torque and angular velocity, $P = T \omega$, Where ω must be expressed in radians per unit time, power is in KW, & torque in N-m.

Shaft Stresses: First, we must find the applied stresses at all points of interest. The largest alternating and mean bending stresses are at the outer surface and are found from

$$\sigma_a = K_f \frac{M_a c}{I} \sigma_m = K_{fm} \frac{M_m c}{I}$$

Where K_f and K_{fm} are the bending-fatigue stress-concentration factors for the alternating and mean components, respectively.

Since the typical shaft is a solid-round cross section, we can substitute for c and I

$$c = r = \frac{d}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad I = \frac{\pi d^4}{64}$$

$$\sigma_a = K_f \frac{32M_a}{\pi d^3} \sigma_m = K_{fm} \frac{32M_m}{\pi d^3}$$

Where d is the local shaft diameter at the section of interest.

The alternating and mean torsional shear stresses are found from

$$\tau_a = K_{fs} \frac{T_a r}{J} \tau_m = K_{fsm} \frac{T_m r}{J}$$

Where K_{fs} and K_{fsm} are the torsional-fatigue stress-concentration factors for the alternating and mean components, respectively.

For a solid-round cross section, we can substitute for r and J

$$r = \frac{d}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad J = \frac{\pi d^4}{32}$$

$$\tau_a = K_{fs} \frac{16T_a}{\pi d^3} \tau_m = K_{fsm} \frac{16T_m}{\pi d^3}$$

Shaft Design: Both stresses and deflection need to be considered in shaft design. Often, deflection can be critical factor, since excessive deflections will cause rapid wear of shaft bearing. Gears, belts, or chains driven from the shaft can also suffer from misalignment induced by shaft deflections. The stresses in a shaft can be calculated locally for various points along the shaft based on known loads and assumed cross-sections. But, the deflection calculations require that the entire shaft geometry be defined. So, a shaft is typically first designed using stress considerations and then the deflections calculated once the geometry is completely defined. The relationship between the shaft's natural frequencies (in both torsion and bending) and the frequency content of the force and torque-time functions can also be critical. If the forcing functions are close infrequency to the shaft's natural frequencies, resonance can create vibrations, high stresses, and large deflections.

Design for Fully Reversed Bending and Steady Torsion

The loading case is a subset of the general case of fluctuating bending and fluctuating torsion, because of the absence of an alternating component of torsional stress, is considered to be a simple multi-axial fatigue case. (However, the presence of local stress concentrations can cause complex multi-axial stresses.) This simple loading case has been experimentally investigated, and data exist for failure of parts so loaded as shown in fig 5. The ASME has defined an approach for the shafts loaded in this manner.

Fig. 5 Results of Fatigue Tests of Steel Specimens Subjected to Combined Bending and Torsion. (Ref. Norton, pg. no. 547)

Preliminary Stage of Shaft Design

- In this proposed research work, the operating speed of the gears is assumed in between 200 – 4000 rpm in order to predict the dynamic response of the geared system for different operating speed. Specifically, below the resonance condition of the geared system. Torque on the pinion tooth is calculated by using empirical equation.

$$F_t = \frac{191 \times 10^5 \times P}{d \times n} \& F_t = \frac{2 T_P}{d_p}, T_P = F_t r_p$$

Therefore, **Design Torque = 300 N-m**

However, for design of massive shaft it is considered as the mean torque acting on the gear tooth **Tm = 350 N-m**. The tangential force component is found from the assumed mean torque and pitch circle diameter of pinion.

Key Design

Introduction: The ASME defines a key as “a demountable machinery part which, when assembled into key-seats, provides a positive means for transmitting torque between the shaft and hub”. Keys are standardized as to size and shape in several styles.

A **parallel key** is a square or rectangular in cross-section and of constant height and width over its length. Parallel keys are the most commonly used. The ANSI and ISO standards each define particular key cross-sectional sizes and key-seat depths as a function of shaft diameter at the key-seat. Square keys are recommended for shafts up to 25 mm diameter and rectangular keys for larger diameters. The parallel key is placed with the half of its height in the shaft and half in the hub. Parallel keys are typically made from standard cold-rolled bar stock.

When the torque changes sign (torque loading is alternating from positive to negative each cycle) then, any clearance between key and keyway will be suddenly taken up with resulting impact and high stresses. This is termed as backlash. A setscrew in the hub, placed at 90° , can hold the hub axially and stabilize the key against backlash. Key length should be less than about 1.5 times shaft diameter to avoid excessive twisting with shaft deflection. **Fig. 6**

A **tapered key** is of constant width but its height varies with a linear of 1/8 in per foot, and it is driven in to a tapered slot in the hub until it locks. It may either have a gib-head to facilitate removal. The taper is a locking one, which means that the friction force between the surfaces holds the key in place axially. The gib head is optional and provides a surface for prying the key out when the small end is not accessible. Tapered keys tend to create eccentricity between the hub and shaft as they drive all the radial clearance to one side.

Fig. 6

A **Woodruff key** is semicircular in plan and of constant width. Woodruff keys are used on smaller shafts. They are self-aligning, so they are preferred for tapered shafts. The

penetration of a woodruff key into the hub is the same as that of a square key i.e, half the key width. The semicircular shape creates a deeper key-seat in the, which resist which resist key rolling, but weakens the shaft compared to a squared or tapered key-seat. Woodruff key widths as a function of shaft diameter are essentially the same as those for square keys. **Fig. 6**

Stresses in Keys

There are two modes of failure in keys: shear and bearing. A shear failure occurs when the key is sheared across its width at the interface between the shaft and hub. Bearing failure occurs by crushing either side in compression.

Shear Failure: The average stress due to direct shear is defined as,

$\tau_{xy} = \frac{F}{A_{\text{shear}}}$, where F is the applied force and A_{shear} is the shear area being cut. In this case A_{shear} is the product of the key's width and length. The force on the key can be found from quotient of the shaft torque and shaft radius. If the shaft torque is constant with time, then, the safety factor can be found by comparing the shear stress to the shear yield strength of the material. If the shaft torque is time varying, then the fatigue failure of key in shear is possible. Then the approach is to compute the mean and alternating shear - stress components and use them to compute mean and alternating Von Mises stresses. Then these can be used in a modified-Goodman diagram to find safety factor.

Bearing Failure: The average bearing stress is defined as

$\sigma_x = \frac{F}{A_{\text{bearing}}}$, where F is the applied force and A_{bearing} is the bearing area is the area of contact between the key side and the shaft or the hub. For square key this will be its half – height times its length. The bearing stress should be calculated using the maximum applied force, whether constant or time varying. Since compressive stresses do not cause fatigue failure, bearing stresses can be considered static. The safety factor is found by comparing the maximum bending stress to the material yield strength in compression.

Key Materials: Because keys are loaded in shear, ductile materials are used. Soft low-carbon steel is the most common choice. Square or rectangular keys are often made from cold-rolled bar stock and merely cut to length.

Key Design: The shaft diameter at the key-seat determines the key width. The key height (or its penetration in to the hub) is also determined by the key width. This leaves only the length of key and the number of keys used per hub as design variables.

It is common to size the key so that it will fail before the key-seat in the shaft fails in the event of an overload. Then the key acts like a shear pin in an outboard motor to protect the more expensive elements from damage. A key is inexpensive and relatively easy to replace if the key-seat is undamaged. This is one reason to use only soft, ductile materials for the key, having lower strength than that of the shaft so that a bearing failure will selectively affect the key rather than the keyway if the system sees an overload beyond its design range.

For this proposed research work, **rectangular parallel key is selected**. The standard dimensions (width and height) is based on dimensions of shaft. The length of key will be decided by considering shear and bearing failure. When shaft dia. d in mm, lies in between 44 –50, then width(mm) \times Height of key (mm) = **12 x 8**

Material for key: low carbon cold rolled steel

Material: C-35

psg. 1.12

Condition: bars & forgings, hardened and tempered

$S_{yt} = 250 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $S_{ut} = 500 \text{ N/mm}^2$,

A **factor of safety 2** will be employed in the absence of exact information about the nature of load. Permissible magnitude of shearing stresses is calculated as follows: according to distortion energy theory yield strength in shear is 0.577 times yield strength in tension, and permissible magnitude of bearing stresses (crushing) is equal to 1.5 – 2.0 times yield strength in tension.

The final dimensions of key are as follows

12 mm (width) \times 8 mm (height) \times 20 mm (length)

TEST SEQUENCE

As per designed data I have manufactured Helical gears of Class 12. The manufactured shafts are now assembled with One Pair of Helical Gear of same class with selected Ball Bearing at designated place. This Shaft gear and bearing assembly is placed in gearbox and assembled with help of Allen key bolts. The input shaft is connected to VFD Drive Motor with help of Flanged coupling. The dynamic balancing of motor shaft and input of gear box are done digitally using a digital dynamic balancer device.

Dynamic test setup is ready for taking the readings. Then we have to set VFD drive is to set for desired RPM. The load is given by rope break dynamometer. When the excitation is in equilibrium then we have measured the vibrations. The vibrations are measured using a FFT Analyzer. This procedure is done for different speeds and at different loads of different Class of Gears.

RESULTS

As per teste data We have found following results.

Class 12 Helical Gears

Speed rmp	LOAD in kg	RMS Acceleration Response m/s^2
700	0	2.5
700	1	3.1
700	2	3.4
700	3	3.4
700	4	3.6
700	5	3.4
900	0	2.8
900	1	3.3
900	2	5.4
900	3	3.2
900	4	3.6
900	5	3.9
1100	0	4.1
1100	1	6.2
1100	2	3.9
1100	3	3.6
1100	4	3.7
1100	5	4.0
1300	0	6.0

1300	1	5.1
1300	2	3.8
1300	3	5.5
1300	4	3.8
1300	5	3.9
1500	0	4.6
1500	1	5.2
1500	2	4.1
1500	3	5.2
1500	4	4.3
1500	5	5.8

Similar tests are conducted at various loading and speed Conditions.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analysis has now become an integral part of Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) and is being extensively used in the analysis and design of many complex real-life systems. While it started off as an extension of matrix methods of structural analysis and was initially perceived as a tool for structural analysis alone, its applications now range from structures to bio-mechanics to electromagnetic field problems. Simple linear static problems as well as highly complex nonlinear transient dynamic problems are effectively solved using the finite element method. The field of finite element analysis has matured and now rests on rigorous mathematical foundation.

Classical analytical methods consider a differential element and develop the governing equations, usually in the form of partial differential equations. When applied to real-life problem situations, it is often difficult to obtain an exact solution to these equations in view of complex geometry and boundary conditions. The finite element method (FEM) can be viewed simply as a method of finding approximate solutions for partial differential equations or as a tool to transform partial differential equations into algebraic equations, which are then easily solved.

The key ideas in the finite element formulation are summarized below:

- To solve any engineering problems, we mostly have 3 methods i.e. analytical, numerical and experimental.
- The analytical method is easy and give accurate solution of the variable field across the domain of the problem.
- The disadvantages of analytical method are, it only gives solution for mostly simple geometries like square, circle and other geometries whose mass moment of inertia or area is mostly given in the form of equations.

When the domain of problem is bigger and don't have standard shape and size the analytical method is quite difficult to handle. In such case the solution for the field variable satisfying both boundary condition and the differential equation is unknown. Hence, we have to begin with some assumed trial solution. The trial solution is assumed such a way that it can satisfy the boundary condition of problem.

CONCLUSION

The Helical Gears of Different class is tested dynamically at different loads. The Vibrations are measured with help of FFT Analyzer. The Value we got from Dynamic Test Setup Rig are formulated in results section. We studied response of various class of gear pairs at different load and speed conditions.

Experimental Results are validated by conducting finite element analysis method.

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